

PREVENTION OF BRUCELLOSIS

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Brucellosis is a zoonotic infection transmitted from animals to humans through contact with infected animals or through consumption of infected meat, milk, and dairy products. The causative agents of the infection are small gram-negative bacteria - brucella, belonging to the II group of pathogenic microorganisms for humans and named after their discoverer - David Bruce. The danger is represented by 4 types of pathogen: B. abortus (in cattle), B. melitensis (in sheep and goats), B. suis (in pigs), B. ovis (in sheep and sheep). The most virulent and significant in the pathology of brucellosis B. melitensis, B. suis, B. abortus (arranged in descending order of pathogenicity). Brucellosis in dogs is caused by brucella species B. canis, bush rats - B. neotomae. The three main types of Brucella are divided into several biotypes. Human brucellosis is mainly caused by 3 species: B. melitensis, B. suis, B. abortus. Human infection with B. canis occurs relatively rarely. Symptoms of brucellosis vary depending on the epizootic situation and the reactivity of the human body. In recent years, several more species of Brucella have been identified, characteristic of cetaceans (B. ceti), pinnipeds (B. pinnipedialis), common voles (B. microti). These three species were registered by the Brucella Taxonomy Subcommittee in September 2008. In addition, a species-specific Brucella isolate was isolated from baboons. The strain is named Brucella papionis.

Brucellosis occurs on all continents in most countries of the world. Especially in the countries of the Mediterranean, Eastern Europe, South and Central America, Africa, Central and South Asia, the Caucasus, the Arabian Peninsula, the Middle East. In these regions, brucellosis is found mainly in cattle (cattle), small cattle (SLC), as well as in wild pigs, bison, elk, and hares. According to the most conservative estimates, more than 300 million of the 1.4 billion cattle in the world are infected with the causative agent of brucellosis. Chronic, often asymptomatic and prolonged course of brucellosis infection in animals makes it difficult to diagnose. Resistance to environmental factors and the exceptional plasticity of the pathogen, in the presence of sufficient relative post-infection immunity, determine the complexity of the fight against infection.

Prevention of brucellosis is based on the implementation of the basic veterinary and sanitary rules for the protection of prosperous farms from the introduction of the infectious agent.

It is necessary to exclude the possibility of contact of healthy livestock with the sick, as well as various groups of livestock on pastures, places of mass congestion of animals and during transportation. It is necessary to carry out planned preventive diagnostic studies and vaccinations.

Live attenuated and inactivated vaccines have received the greatest distribution for immunization of animals against brucellosis. In addition to whole-cell vaccines against brucellosis, preparations based on antigens isolated from *Brucella*, recombinant and DNA vaccines are being developed. Abroad, the American live vaccine from the non-agglutinogenic strain of *B. abortus* RB-51, which has stable biological and immunogenic properties, is widely used.

In recent years, in our country, small cattle have been immunized mainly with a live vaccine from the *B. melitensis* Rev-1 strain, much less with a vaccine from the *B. abortus* 19 strain, and large cattle with a vaccine from the *B. abortus* strain 82, less often from *B. abortus* strains. *B. abortus* 75/79-AB.

An analysis of the tactics of conducting preventive vaccination and people from 2015 to 2019 allows us to divide the subjects of the Surkhandarya region into five groups.

In the first group, 21% of small and 32% of cattle belonging to agricultural enterprises were immunized against brucellosis. Immunoprophylaxis of both animal species was carried out regardless of the presence of a sick herd of small ruminants. In the Surkhandarya region, the formation of foci of sheep brucellosis was associated with unauthorized importation of animals. The incidence of human brucellosis was 24.2% of the total number of patients recorded in the country during the analyzed period. The analysis showed a slight decrease in the registration of fresh cases of brucellosis (by 1.2 times). Consequently, carrying out immunoprophylaxis of small and large cattle on farms of only one form of ownership (animals of agricultural enterprises) only restrained a further increase in the incidence of people, but did not significantly affect it.

Zoonotic infections, which have become of great importance for public health in recent years, require the complexity of interdepartmental measures taken by the state veterinary and sanitary and epidemiological services in order to establish the causes of the disease, transmission factors and the breadth of susceptible contingents.

Only close, objective interaction of these services at all levels of supervision will create a reliable system for the protection of infection and disease in animals (the source and reservoir of zoonotic infections), and this, in turn, will further minimize the risk of infection in humans.

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